

```
> library(readxl)
> all <- read_excel("Documents/Publications/Mc Con Dep/data/
f1_short_m_5_2021.xlsx")
> View(all)
> str(all)
> all$id<-as.factor(all$id)
> all$fam<-as.factor(all$fam)
> all$str<-as.factor(all$str)
> save.image("~/Documents/Publications/Mc Con Dep/data/all.RData")
```

```
> library(lme4)
> library(car)
```

1. test for nutrition sensitivity of boy size and trait size

```
> wa.fed<-lmer(wa~totfed+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(wa.fed,type=3)

> white.fed<-lmer(white~totfed+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(white.fed,type=3)

> tip.fed<-lmer(tip~totfed+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(tip.fed,type=3)

> blue.fed<-lmer(blue~totfed+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(blue.fed,type=3)

> sqmfl.fed<-lmer(sqmfl~totfed+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(sqmfl.fed,type=3)
```

2. test for body size dependence of trait size using standardized trait size

```
> std_white.wa<-lmer(std_white~wa+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(std_white.wa,type=3)
>coef(std_white.wa)
>
> std_blue.wa<-lmer(std_blue~wa+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(std_blue.wa,type=3)
>coef(std_blue.wa)
>
> std_sqmfl.wa<-lmer(std_sqmfl~wa+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(std_sqmfl.wa,type=3)
>coef(std_sqmfl.wa)

> std_white.fat<-lmer(std_white~totfat+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(std_white.fat,type=3)
>coef(std_white.fat)
>
```

```

> std_blue.fat<-lmer(std_blue~totfat+(1lfam),data=all)
> Anova(std_blue.fat,type=3)
>coef(std_blue.fat)
>
> std_sqmfl.fat<-lmer(std_sqmfl~totfat+(1lfam),data=all)
> Anova(std_sqmfl.fat,type=3)
>coef(std_sqmfl.fat)

```

3. compare body size dependence between different traits

```

> library(readxl)
> cd <- read_excel("Documents/Publications/Mc Con Dep/data/
f1_long_m_5_2021.xlsx")
> View(cd)
> str(cd)
> cd$id<-as.factor(cd$id)
> cd$fam<-as.factor(cd$fam)
> mfl<-subset(cd,cd$trait=="white"|cd$trait=="sqmfl")
> blue<-subset(cd,cd$trait=="white"|cd$trait=="blue")
>
> trait.cd<-lmer(std_resp~trait*wa+(1lfam)+(1lid:fam),data=cd)
> Anova(trait.cd,type=3)

> white.blue.cd<-lmer(std_resp~trait*wa+(1lfam)+(1lid:fam),data=blue)
> Anova(white.blue.cd,type=3)

> white.mfl.cd<-lmer(std_resp~trait*wa+(1lfam)+(1lid:fam),data=mfl)
> Anova(white.mfl.cd,type=3)

```

4. test for body size dependence of color parameters

```

> bri.wa<-lmer(bri~wa+(1lfam),data=all)
> Anova(bri.wa,type=3)

> bri.fat<-lmer(bri~tptfat+(1lfam),data=all)
> Anova(bri.fat,type=3)

```

5. test for signaling content independent of body size, standardized residual from trait area~body size regression calculated in excel

```

> white.mus<-lmer(stdr.white.wa~mus+(1lfam),data=all)
> Anova(white.mus,type=3)

> white.bfat<-lmer(stdr.white.wa~bodyfat+(1lfam),data=all)
> Anova(white.bfat,type=3)

```

```

## exclude one outlier for fat reserve ##
bfat<-subset(all, all$id!="850")

```

```
> bfat$bodyfat<-1000*bfat$bodyfat
> white.bfat<-lmer(stdr.white.wa~bodyfat+(1|fam),data=bfat)
> Anova(white.bfat)
```

6. test how amount of total fat (fat reserve+wing wax) vary with amount of food fed

```
> fat.fed<-lmer(totfat~totfed+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(fat.fed,type=3)
```

7. examine how fat reserve and wing wax change with body size

```
> wfat.wa<-lmer(wingfat~wa+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(wfat.wa,type=3)
>
> bfat.wa<-lmer(bodyfat~wa+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(bfat.wa,type=3)
```

8. examine whether wax density (amount of wax per unit area of white wing band) change with body size

```
> wfatden<-all$wingfat/all$white
> den.wa<-lmer(wfatden~wa+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(den.wa,type=3)
```

9. examine how proportion of fat allocated to the white wing band change with body size

```
> all$propwfat<-1-all$propbfat
> all$asin_propwfat<-asin(sqrt(all$propwfat))
>
> propwfat.wa<-lmer(asin_propwfat~wa+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(propwfat.wa,type=3)
```

10. examine how female body size, wing tip size and male wing tip size change with total food fed

```
> library(readxl)
> tip <- read_excel("Documents/Publications/Mc Con Dep/data/tip.xlsx")
> View(tip)
> str(tip)
>
> tip$id<-as.factor(tip$id)
> tip$fam<-as.factor(tip$fam)
> tip$sex<-as.factor(tip$sex)
> tip$trait<-as.factor(tip$trait)

> m<-subset(tip,tip$sex=="M")
> f<-subset(tip,tip$sex=="F")
```

```
> tipa<-subset(tip,tip$trait=="tip")
> sqmfl<-subset(tip,tip$trait=="sqmfl")
> m.tipa<-subset(tip,tip$trait=="tip"&tip$sex=="M")
> f.tipa<-subset(tip,tip$trait=="tip"&tip$sex=="F")
> save.image("~/Documents/Publications/Mc Con Dep/data/tip.RData")
```

```
> library(readxl)
> ftip <- read_excel("Documents/Publications/Mc Con Dep/data/
tip_short_f_6_2021.xlsx")
> View(ftip)
> str(ftip)
> ftip$id<-as.factor(ftip$id)
> ftip$fam<-as.factor(ftip$fam)
> ftip$sex<-as.factor(ftip$sex)
> save.image("~/Documents/Publications/Mc Con Dep/data/ftip.RData")
```

```
> library(car)
> library(lme4)
>
```

```
> wa.fed<-lmer(wa~totfed+(1|fam),data=ftip)
> Anova(wa.fed,type=3)
```

```
> tip.fed<-lmer(resp~totfed*sex+(1|fam),data=tipa)
> Anova(tip.fed,type=3)
>
> tip.fed<-lmer(resp~totfed+sex+(1|fam),data=tipa)
> Anova(tip.fed,type=3)
```

12. examine how tip size and brightness change with body size

```
> m.tip.wa<-lmer(resp~wa+(1|fam),data=m.tipa)
> Anova(m.tip.wa,type=3)
> coef(m.tip.wa)
```

```
> f.tip.wa<-lmer(resp~wa+(1|fam),data=f.tipa)
> Anova(f.tip.wa,type=3)
> coef(f.tip.wa0)
```

```
> m.tip.mfl<-lmer(std_resp~wa*trait+(1|fam),data=m)
> Anova(m.tip.mfl,type=3)
> coef(m.tip.mfl)
>
> f.tip.mfl<-lmer(std_resp~wa*trait+(1|fam),data=f)
> Anova(f.tip.mfl,type=3)
> coef(f.tip.mfl)
```

```
> tip.mfl<-lmer(std_resp~wa*sex+(1|fam),data=tipa)
> Anova(tip.mfl,type=3)
```

```
> bri.wa<-lmer(bri~wa+(1|fam),data=ftip)
> Anova(bri.wa,type=3)
```

13. examine how total fat, fat reserve and wax on the wing change with food fed and body size in females

```
> fat.fed<-lmer(totfat~totfed+(1|fam),data=ftip)
> Anova(fat.fed,type=3)
```

```
> wfat.wa<-lmer(wingfat~wa+(1|fam),data=ftip)
> Anova(wfat.wa,type=3)
```

```
>
```

```
> bfat.wa<-lmer(bodyfat~wa+(1|fam),data=ftip)
> Anova(bfat.wa,type=3)
```

```
> wfatden<-ftip$wingfat/ftip$tip
> den.wa<-lmer(wfatden~wa+(1|fam),data=ftip)
> Anova(den.wa,type=3)
```

14. examine how proportion of fat allocated to the white wing tip change with body size in females

```
> f.propwfat.wa<-lmer(asin_propwfat~wa+(1|fam),data=ftip)
> Anova(f.propwfat.wa)
```

15. for supplementary results

```
> dev.trt<-lmer(devday~trt+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(dev.trt)
```

```
>
```

```
> trtdur.trt<-lmer(trtday~trt+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(trtdur.trt,type=3)
```

```
>
```

```
> fed.trt<-lmer(totfed~trt+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(fed.trt,type=3)
```

```
>
```

```
> wa.trt<-lmer(wa~trt+(1|fam),data=all)
> Anova(wa.trt,type=3)
```